

Transition-Based Forest Carbon Accounting in a Tropical Forest Using Sentinel-2 Remote Sensing and GIS

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Abstract

Spatially explicit forest carbon assessments remain limited in many developing countries due to data scarcity. This study enhances IPCC Tier-1 carbon accounting by integrating high-resolution Sentinel-2 (10 m) imagery with a transition-resolved stock-difference framework and Monte Carlo uncertainty propagation to quantify LULC-driven carbon dynamics in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest, Myanmar (2017–2024). The key innovation lies in applying a transition-resolved, uncertainty-aware Tier-1 approach that moves beyond conventional area-based accounting in data-limited tropical forest contexts. The findings show significant forest conversion, resulting in a net biomass carbon loss of 32,115.23 t C ($\approx 117,756$ t CO₂-eq), with transitions to flooded vegetation and rangeland accounting for the majority of emissions. The findings demonstrate the potential of enhanced Tier-1 methodologies combined with Earth observation data to support REDD+ MRV in developing regions.

Keywords: *Land-use/land-cover (LULC), Forest carbon dynamics, Sentinel-2 remote sensing, IPCC Tier-1 carbon accounting, REDD+ MRV.*

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Introduction

Environmental change driven by deforestation, agricultural expansion, and urbanization is a major global challenge, contributing substantially to greenhouse gas emissions and accelerating climate change (Dutta & Bandopadhyay, 2022; Kumar et al., 2025). Land-use transformations disrupt ecosystem functioning and reduce the capacity of forests to act as long-term carbon sinks. Tropical forests are particularly important in this context, as they store large amounts of above- and below-ground carbon yet are highly vulnerable to degradation that can rapidly shift them from net carbon sinks to net carbon sources (Fan et al., 2008).

Myanmar exemplifies these challenges, having experienced sustained forest loss over recent decades due to agricultural expansion, subsistence farming, and weak forest governance. Between 2000 and 2005, the country recorded an average annual deforestation rate of approximately 0.68%, reflecting continued pressure on forest resources and associated carbon stocks (F. J. Liu et al., 2016). These trends heighten

national vulnerability to climate change and underscore the need for improved monitoring of forest dynamics and carbon emissions.

Within Myanmar, the Bago Mountain Range represents a critical forested landscape undergoing rapid transformation. Forest cover in this region, including the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest, declined markedly from about 71,240 ha in 2000 to 40,891 ha in 2017, alongside the expansion of degraded forest areas (Kyaw, 2018). Despite its protected status, Shwe Laung Reserved Forest illustrates the broader vulnerability of forest reserves in central Myanmar to illegal logging, agricultural encroachment, and fragmentation-driven carbon loss.

Empirical forest carbon assessments in Myanmar and much of Southeast Asia remain constrained by limited field inventories, fragmented historical data, and weak long-term monitoring capacity (F.-J. Liu et al., 2016; Naing Tun et al., 2021). The Shwe Laung Reserved Forest typifies these data-limited tropical landscapes, characterized by monsoonal climates, mixed deciduous–evergreen forests, and degradation-driven change common across the region (Hansen et al., 2016; Kyaw, 2018). Under such data-limited conditions, integrating Sentinel-2–derived land-use/land-cover (LULC) change with IPCC Tier-1 carbon accounting offers a transparent and policy-consistent framework for spatially explicit estimation of carbon gains and losses compatible with REDD+ measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV) requirements (Baasansuren et al., 2019; Hunka et al., 2024).

Previous studies in the Bago region largely focused on periods ending around 2015–2017 and relied on Landsat-based or national-scale assessments (De Sy et al., 2019; Fao, 2018; Hansen et al., 2013). There were no spatially explicit assessments for Shwe Laung RF that included data from 2024, and while these studies showed long-term trends in deforestation, they were unable to account for post-2017 dynamics such as recent degradation, hydrological change, and partial forest rebound (De Sy et al., 2019; Fao, 2018). Consequently, post-2017 dynamics, including recent degradation, hydrological change, and partial forest recovery, remain poorly quantified, and few studies have linked LULC transitions explicitly to IPCC-compatible carbon accounting relevant for REDD+ applications (Achard et al., 2014; Baasansuren et al., 2019). By analyzing 2017–2024 Sentinel-2 imagery and integrating transition-resolved LULC matrices with IPCC Tier-1 biomass coefficients, this study provides the first up-to-date, policy-consistent assessment of forest carbon dynamics in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest. The approach enables spatial attribution of carbon losses and gains while maintaining consistency with national greenhouse-gas inventory requirements.

Against this backdrop, this study quantifies recent LULC dynamics and associated forest carbon changes in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest using Sentinel-2 imagery and an IPCC Tier-1 stock-difference framework, and examines implications for sustainable forest management and climate-change mitigation in data-limited tropical forest landscapes.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The Shwe Laung Reserved Forest (SLRF) is located in Kyauktaga Township, Bago Region, Myanmar, between 18°50'00"–19°05'00" N and 96°45'00"–97°05'00" E, covering approximately 19,000 ha (Figure 1). The reserve forms part of the Bago Yoma range and is characterized by elevations of ~150–450 m a.s.l., a monsoonal climate, and mixed deciduous–evergreen forest formations (Win et al., 2025). Mean annual temperatures range from ~25–32 °C, and annual precipitation varies between ~2,000 and 3,500 mm. Despite its protected status, SLRF experiences pressures from agricultural encroachment, fuelwood extraction, and localized logging, compounded by limited accessibility and monitoring capacity (Kyaw, 2018; Toda et al., 2023). These characteristics make the site a critical landscape for assessing land-cover

change, forest dynamics, and carbon-emission patterns using remote-sensing approaches (Liang et al., 2025).

Figure 1. GIS location of Shwe Laung Reserved Forest in Bago Region, Myanmar

Remote Sensing Data and Pre-processing

The Sentinel-2 Level-2A (Lyakhov et al., 2025) imagery was utilized in this study. Land-use/land-cover (LULC) data for 2017 and 2024 were obtained from a pre-classified Sentinel-2 10 m LULC product derived from Level-2A surface reflectance imagery and were directly used for LULC change detection and carbon emission analysis (Pham et al., 2020; Robertson & Bakimchandra, 2024). Post-classification change detection was applied to assess spatiotemporal LULC dynamics by comparing discrete LULC maps from different periods, a widely adopted approach that minimizes the influence of sensor-specific and atmospheric variations (Abdulaziz et al., 2009; Zewdie & Csaplovics, 2014). The classified LULC maps were spatially overlaid within the ArcGIS environment to generate pixel-level transition layers and corresponding attribute tables that describe the direction and magnitude of land-cover conversions between 2017 and 2024. These attribute tables were exported to Microsoft Excel to construct area-based LULC transition matrices and to quantify class-specific rates of change (Mustaquim & Islam, 2025). Carbon stock changes associated with each transition pathway were then estimated by integrating the LULC transition matrices with IPCC Tier-1 above-ground biomass, enabling a consistent and policy-relevant quantification of carbon loss and gain attributable to land-cover dynamics in data-limited tropical forest environments (Gagula et al., 2025; Gao et al., 2025).

Table 1. Class Definitions

Value	Name	Description
1	Water	Areas where water was predominantly present throughout the year may not cover areas with sporadic or ephemeral water; contains little to no sparse vegetation, no rock outcrop nor built up features like docks; examples: rivers, ponds, lakes, oceans, flooded salt plains.

2	Trees	Any significant clustering of tall (~15 feet or higher) dense vegetation, typically with a closed or dense canopy; examples: wooded vegetation, clusters of dense tall vegetation within savannas, plantations, swamp or mangroves (dense/tall vegetation with ephemeral water or canopy too thick to detect water underneath).
4	Flooded vegetation	Areas of any type of vegetation with obvious intermixing of water throughout a majority of the year; seasonally flooded area that is a mix of grass/shrub/trees/bare ground; examples: flooded mangroves, emergent vegetation, rice paddies, and other heavily irrigated and inundated agriculture.
5	Crops	Humans planted/plotted cereals, grasses, and crops not at tree height; examples: corn, wheat, soy, fallow plots of structured land.
7	Built Area	Human-made structures; major road and rail networks; large homogenous impervious surfaces, including parking structures, office buildings, and residential housing; examples: houses, dense villages/towns/cities, paved roads, and asphalt.
8	Bare ground	Areas of rock or soil with very sparse to no vegetation for the entire year; large areas of sand and deserts with no to little vegetation; examples: exposed rock or soil, desert, and sand dunes, dry salt flats/pans, dried lake beds, mines.
9	Snow/Ice	Large homogenous areas of permanent snow or ice, typically only in mountain areas or highest latitudes; examples: glaciers, permanent snowpack, snow fields.
10	Clouds	No land cover information due to persistent cloud cover.
11	Rangeland	Open areas covered in homogenous grasses with little to no taller vegetation; wild cereals and grasses with no obvious human plotting (i.e., not a plotted field); examples: natural meadows and fields with sparse to no tree cover, open savanna with few to no trees, parks/golf courses/lawns, pastures. Mix of small clusters of plants or single plants dispersed on a landscape that shows exposed soil or rock; scrub-filled clearings within dense forests that are clearly not taller than trees; examples: moderate to sparse cover of bushes, shrubs, and tufts of grass, savannas with very sparse grasses, trees, or other plants.

Source: Sentinel-2L2A <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=cfc7609de5f478eb7666240902d4d3d>

Note: A land use focus does not provide the same level of spatial detail as a land cover map. As such, for the built area classification, yards, parks, and groves will appear as built area rather than trees or rangeland classes.

LULC Classification and Data Acquisition

To quantify spatiotemporal landscape dynamics in the Shwe Laung Forest Reserve, LULC analysis was conducted using Sentinel-2 Level-2A surface reflectance imagery for the 2017 and 2024 epochs. Recent advances in high-resolution satellite remote sensing have demonstrated the reliability of Sentinel-2 Level-2A imagery approaches for detecting LULC dynamics and supporting ecosystem and carbon-related assessments (Jocca¹ et al., 2025; D Phiri et al., 2020). Sentinel-2 data were selected for their 10 m spatial resolution and suitability for monitoring forest dynamics in heterogeneous tropical landscapes (Drusch et al., 2012; Immitzer et al., 2016). Six ecologically representative LULC classes, trees, flooded vegetation, croplands, bare ground, rangeland, and water were defined to capture dominant land-cover types and major forest-degradation pathways (Change, 2006; Lu et al., 2004; Rashid & Iqbal, 2018). All datasets were processed in the WGS 84 coordinate reference system at a uniform 10 m spatial resolution. Seasonally comparable imagery was selected to minimize atmospheric and phenological uncertainties (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014).

Accuracy Assessment and Classification Reliability

Formal accuracy assessment using independent ground reference data was not performed due to the absence of contemporaneous field observations and high-resolution reference data for the study area. Classification reliability was therefore ensured using a validated, pre-classified Sentinel-2 LULC product, supplemented by consistency checks between the 2017 and 2024 maps, visual inspection, and logical

validation of dominant transition pathways. Given the focus on post-classification change detection and transition-based carbon accounting, temporal consistency was prioritized over single-date accuracy metrics, consistent with practice in data-limited tropical forest studies (Lu Corresponding author et al., 2004; D Phiri et al., 2020; Darius Phiri et al., 2020).

LULC Change Detection and Transition Analysis

Post-classification change detection was employed to quantify spatiotemporal LULC dynamics (Krivoguz, 2025) between 2017 and 2024. Independently classified maps were spatially aligned and overlaid at the pixel level to derive stable areas and directional land-cover transitions. Raster algebra and attribute table extraction were used to generate area-based LULC transition matrices describing the magnitude and direction of change among classes (Krivoguz, 2025). This post-classification framework minimizes sensor- and atmosphere-related effects and directly supports transition-based carbon stock estimation (Jantawong et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2025).

IPCC Tier-1 Forest Biomass Parameterization

Forest and non-forest biomass values were parameterized using IPCC Tier-1 default above-ground biomass (AGB) coefficients appropriate for tropical Asia. Due to the absence of spatially explicit forest age data, all forest pixels were treated as a single Trees class and parameterized using a representative Tier-1 biomass value for secondary tropical forests, consistent with IPCC guidance for data-limited forest carbon accounting (Change, 1995; Change, 2007). Given the dominance of secondary forests in SLRF, an AGB value of 131.6 t d.m. ha⁻¹ was assigned to the Trees class. Flooded vegetation and croplands were assigned 20 t d.m. ha⁻¹, rangeland 6.2 t d.m. ha⁻¹, and bare ground and water bodies 0 t d.m. ha⁻¹, consistent with IPCC guidance (Baasansuren et al., 2019). This parameterization provides a transparent and policy-consistent basis for carbon accounting in data-limited regions.

According to the IPCC (2006) Guidelines, the default carbon stock for annual cropland is 10 t d.m. ha⁻¹, which, using the IPCC default carbon fraction of 0.47, corresponds to approximately 20 t d.m. ha⁻¹ of above-ground biomass. However, many studies apply a rounded Tier-1 value of about 20 t d.m. ha⁻¹ to represent the combined above-ground and below-ground biomass of productive croplands such as cereals, paddy rice, maize, and mixed cropping systems (Amon et al., 2021; Change, 2006; Lal, 2004; Paustian et al., 2016; Smith et al., 2008).

The biomass value for tropical moist grassland is given as 6.2 t d.m. ha⁻¹ in the IPCC (2006) guidelines and is often increased to about 20 t d.m. ha⁻¹ to represent flooded or marshy grasslands with denser vegetation. The figure is set at 20 t d.m. ha⁻¹ for flooded or marshy grasslands, as these ecosystems store more biomass than typical dry grasslands (Change, 2006; Rozendaal et al., 2022).

Similarly, the AGB values assigned to flooded vegetation (20 t d.m. ha⁻¹), rangeland (6.2 t d.m. ha⁻¹), and cropland (20 t d.m. ha⁻¹) follow IPCC Tier-1 default coefficients for non-forest land use classes, which account for their low woody biomass and limited long-term carbon storage potential. Assigning 0 t d.m. ha⁻¹ to bare ground and water bodies is consistent with IPCC guidance and widely adopted practice, as these classes contain negligible above-ground biomass (Baasansuren et al., 2019) (Schietecatte et al., 2025; Van Meerbeek et al., 2019).

Carbon Stock Estimation and Emissions Accounting

Forest carbon stock change was quantified using the IPCC Tier-1 stock-difference approach, which estimates net changes in biomass carbon as the balance between carbon gains from forest regeneration and carbon losses resulting from deforestation and forest degradation (Baasansuren et al., 2019; IPCC, 2006).

Biomass Change by LULC Transitions

For each LULC transition, the change in above-ground biomass (ΔAGB) was calculated as the difference between the final and initial IPCC Tier-1 default biomass values:

$$\Delta AGB = AGB_{\text{final}} - AGB_{\text{initial}} \quad (1)$$

where AGB_{final} and AGB_{initial} (t d.m. ha⁻¹) correspond to the IPCC Tier-1 above-ground biomass values assigned to the LULC classes in 2024 and 2017, respectively.

Total biomass change ($\Delta \text{Biomass}$, t) for each transition was then calculated as:

$$\Delta \text{Biomass} = \Delta AGB \times \text{Area} \quad (2)$$

where Area (ha) represents the spatial extent of the corresponding LULC transition derived from the transition matrix.

Conversion from Biomass to Carbon

Biomass change was converted to carbon stock change using the IPCC-recommended carbon fraction of 0.47:

$$\Delta C = \Delta \text{Biomass} \times 0.47 \quad (3)$$

Carbon gains (ΔC_{G}) were attributed to transitions from non-forest to forest classes, while carbon losses (ΔC_{L}) were attributed to transitions from forest to non-forest classes. Transitions between identical land-cover classes were assigned zero net biomass change.

Conversion to CO₂-Equivalent Emissions

Net biomass carbon change was converted to carbon dioxide equivalent emissions using the molecular weight ratio of CO₂ to C (44/12 = 3.67), such that $\text{CO}_2\text{-eq} = \Delta C_{\text{B}} \times 3.67$, consistent with IPCC greenhouse-gas reporting conventions.

$$\text{CO}_2\text{-eq} = \Delta C_{\text{B}} \times 44/12 \quad (4)$$

where:

44 is the molecular weight of CO₂ (12 for C + 32 for O₂), 12 is the atomic weight of carbon.

This transition-based stock-difference framework enables spatially explicit, policy-relevant quantification of forest carbon emissions and removals consistent with IPCC Tier-1 guidance and REDD+ measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV) requirements in data-limited tropical forest environments (Achard et al., 2014; Berhanu et al., 2023; Change, 2006; De Sy et al., 2019; Eggleston et al., 2006; Hunka et al., 2024; Rozendaal et al., 2022).

Monte Carlo implementation

Monte Carlo simulation was applied to evaluate the robustness of carbon estimates under plausible uncertainty ranges in LULC transition areas and IPCC Tier-1 biomass parameters (Change, 2006). For each transition, 10,000 simulations were run, where each iteration randomly selected:

Area \in [Area_min, Area_max]

AGB_forest \in [AGB_min, AGB_max]

AGB_non-forest \in [AGB_min, AGB_max] (Strîmbu et al., 2023)

Carbon change for iteration i was calculated as:

$$\Delta C_i = \text{Area}_i \times (\text{AGB}_{\text{final}} - \text{AGB}_{\text{initial}}) \times 0.47 \quad (5)$$

This Monte Carlo method propagates uncertainty in input parameters through repeated random sampling, consistent with established practice in greenhouse gas uncertainty analysis (S. Schulte et al., 2024).

Monte Carlo simulation is widely used to propagate uncertainty in greenhouse-gas accounting by randomly sampling uncertain input variables and quantifying their effects on final emission or carbon stock estimates (Brasika et al., 2025; Simon Schulte et al., 2024). This approach ensures that the uncertainty propagated through the model accurately reflects realistic variability in key parameters, supporting robust carbon accounting outcomes (Kang et al., 2025).

Although the IPCC Guidelines, which formally describe Monte Carlo uncertainty propagation for inventory categories, predate 2020, they remain the authoritative framework for greenhouse-gas inventory methods and are widely referenced in recent 2020–2025 research assessing or applying Monte Carlo methods (Baasansuren et al., 2019).

Uncertainty outcomes are summarized using distributional statistics derived from Monte Carlo simulations, including the median and the 2.5th–97.5th percentile interval.

Net carbon balance calculation

Total forest carbon losses (ΔC_L) across all transitions and total carbon gains (ΔC_G) from forest regeneration were aggregated and combined as:

$$\Delta C_B = \Delta C_G - \Delta C_L \quad (6)$$

Across all uncertainty scenarios:

$$\Delta C_B < 0$$

The forest remained a net carbon source, demonstrating robustness to parameter uncertainty.

Carbon stock change was therefore estimated using the IPCC Tier-1 stock-difference method, with above-ground biomass changes calculated for each LULC transition and uncertainty propagated using Monte Carlo simulation ($n = 10,000$) (Brasika et al., 2025; Change, 2006; Holdaway et al., 2014; Hynek et al., 2024; Ipcc, 2006; Metsaranta et al., 2017).

Uncertainty, accuracy considerations, and limitations

Uncertainty in carbon change estimates primarily stems from the reliance on IPCC Tier-1 biomass coefficients instead of local measurements, which affects the accuracy of forest structure representation. Additional ambiguity arises in LULC classification, particularly in delineating forest from other vegetation types in monsoon-affected areas. This analysis focuses on above-ground biomass, potentially neglecting below-ground and soil carbon pools. Classification reliability was ensured through consistency checks rather than formal accuracy metrics due to the lack of field reference data. The study employs Monte Carlo simulation to account for uncertainty in transition areas and biomass coefficients, producing 10,000 realizations to evaluate the impact of LULC and parameter uncertainties on carbon estimates. Despite limitations, the findings indicate a persistent negative net biomass carbon balance ($\Delta C_B < 0$) across scenarios, reinforcing the robustness of the study's conclusions.

Results

Figure 2. LULC classes of 2017, 2024, and LULC Transition maps in SLRF

Land-Use Land-Cover Dynamics (2017–2024)

The LULC maps derived from Sentinel-2 imagery reveal that forest cover remained the dominant land-cover class in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest throughout the study period (Figure 2). However, notable spatial reorganization occurred between 2017 and 2024, as reflected by the LULC transition matrix (Table 3). Of the total forest area mapped in 2017 (18,314.20 ha), 17,081.10 ha remained unchanged as forest in 2024, indicating a high level of persistence. Despite this overall stability, measurable forest losses were observed through transitions from Trees to non-forest classes.

The most substantial forest conversion pathway was the transition from trees to flooded vegetation, accounting for 866.15 ha, followed by transitions from trees to water (5.53 ha) and from trees to crops (1.77 ha). These transitions indicate that forest degradation and hydrological change were the dominant mechanisms of forest loss rather than direct large-scale agricultural expansion. Flooded vegetation exhibited comparatively lower stability, with 1,284.45 ha persisting unchanged, while minor transitions occurred toward forest (0.49 ha) and water (1.07 ha). Water bodies showed limited persistence (48.23 ha), with most water-related transitions directed toward flooded vegetation (404.25 ha), reflecting strong

hydrological variability across the landscape. Cropland occupied a relatively small proportion of the study area, with 30.83 ha remaining stable and minor bidirectional exchanges with forest and water classes.

Overall, the LULC transition matrix indicates that forest loss during 2017–2024 was spatially limited but non-negligible, with degradation toward flooded vegetation representing the principal land-cover change pathway.

Carbon Losses from Forest Conversion

Carbon losses associated with forest conversion were quantified using IPCC Tier-1 default biomass coefficients and a transition-based stock-difference approach (Table 4). Total carbon losses (ΔC_L) reached 66,884.07 t C between 2017 and 2024. The largest contribution originated from transitions from trees to flooded vegetation, accounting for 45,431.25 t C (68.0%), driven by extensive conversion (866.15 ha) and a sharp decline in above-ground biomass from 131.6 to 20 t d.m. ha⁻¹. Transitions from trees to rangeland represented the second major pathway, contributing 21,018.06 t C (31.4%). In contrast, transitions from trees to water and from trees to crops contributed only marginal losses of 0.5% and 0.1%, respectively. No net carbon change was assigned to unchanged forest areas, confirming that emissions were attributable to forest conversion.

Carbon Gains from Forest Regeneration

Carbon gains from forest regeneration (ΔC_G) totaled 34,768.84 t C between 2017 and 2024 (Table 5), remaining far lower than carbon losses. Regeneration was dominated by transitions from rangeland to trees, contributing 34,403.11 t C (99.0%) over 583.72 ha. Minor gains arose from transitions from crops to trees (221.51 t C; 0.64%), from bare ground to trees (131.19 t C; 0.38%), from flooded vegetation to trees (25.91 t C; 0.07%), and from water to trees (6.12 t C; 0.02%). Overall, regeneration was insufficient to offset forest-conversion losses.

Net Biomass Carbon Change and CO₂-Equivalent Emissions

Combining carbon losses and gains, the net change in above-ground biomass carbon (ΔC_B) between 2017 and 2024 was -32,115.23 t C, indicating a pronounced net carbon loss from the forest ecosystem. When expressed as carbon dioxide equivalents using the IPCC conversion factor (44/12), this corresponds to net emissions of approximately 117,755.84 t CO₂-eq over the seven years. Despite measurable forest regeneration, carbon gains were insufficient to compensate for losses driven by forest degradation and conversion, resulting in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest acting as a net carbon source during the study period.

CO₂-Equivalent

Table 6 summarizes uncertainty-bounded biomass carbon losses from forest-to-non-forest transitions estimated using an IPCC Tier-1 stock-difference framework with Monte Carlo uncertainty propagation. Carbon losses increase systematically from minimum to maximum scenarios due to combined uncertainty in transition areas ($\pm 10\%$) and above-ground biomass coefficients ($\pm 15\text{--}25\%$). Losses are dominated by transitions from trees to flooded vegetation (median: -45,431 t C; -166,233 t CO₂-eq), followed by transitions from trees to rangeland (-21,018 t C; -77,126 t CO₂-eq), while other pathways contribute marginally. Across all scenarios, forest conversion remains a net source of atmospheric CO₂, demonstrating the robustness of the central estimates and highlighting the value of transition-resolved Sentinel-2 analysis with Monte Carlo-based uncertainty treatment for IPCC Tier-1 carbon assessment in data-limited tropical regions.

Net biomass carbon change under uncertainty

Table 7 presents the uncertainty-bounded net biomass carbon balance (ΔC_B) derived from integrating carbon losses (ΔC_L) from forest-to-non-forest transitions with carbon gains (ΔC_G) from regeneration using the IPCC Tier-1 stock-difference framework. Across all scenarios, ΔC_L consistently exceeds ΔC_G , resulting in a negative net carbon balance, with a median loss of $-32,115.23$ t C. Even under best-case assumptions, the system remains a net carbon source, while worst-case estimates indicate substantial carbon depletion. These results confirm that forest conversion, dominated by transitions from trees to flooded vegetation and from trees to rangeland, overwhelms regrowth-related gains, demonstrating the robustness of the net emission signal under plausible uncertainty bounds and highlighting the value of transition-resolved Sentinel-2 analysis with Monte Carlo uncertainty propagation for Tier-1 carbon assessment in data-limited tropical regions.

The Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis

The Monte Carlo uncertainty results (10,000 iterations) for biomass carbon stock change related to several land-use transitions are summarized in Table 8. Forest conversion to non-forest uses consistently results in carbon losses, with conversion to flooded vegetation representing the largest emission pathway, followed by conversion to rangeland. In contrast, transitions from non-forest land to forest show positive carbon gains, dominated by forest regeneration on rangeland. Across all transitions, the direction of carbon change remains consistent within the 95% uncertainty intervals, indicating robust results. Overall, the study region has a net biomass carbon loss because carbon losses from forest conversion outweigh gains from regeneration.

Tables 4. Carbon Losses (ΔC_L) from Forest Conversion, 2017–2024

Transition (Forest → Non-forest)	Area (ha)	AGB ₂₀₁₇ (t d.m. ha ⁻¹)	AGB ₂₀₂₄ (t d.m. ha ⁻¹)	Δ AGB (t d.m. ha ⁻¹)	Δ Biomass (t)	ΔC_L (t C)
Trees -Water	5.53	131.6	0	-131.6	-727.94	-342.13
Trees - Flooded vegetation	866.15	131.6	20	-111.6	-96,662.23	-45,431.25
Trees -Crops	1.77	131.6	20	-111.6	-197.08	-92.63
Trees - Trees (no change)	17,081.10	131.6	131.6	0	0	0
Trees - Rangeland	356.61	131.6	6.2	-125.4	-44,719.27	-21,018.06

Δ AGB = AGB₂₀₂₄ – AGB₂₀₁₇ ΔC_L denotes carbon losses from forest conversion and was calculated as Δ Biomass \times 0.47. Values represent the total carbon losses accumulated over the period 2017–2024.

Table 5. Carbon Gains (ΔC_G) from forest regeneration, 2017–2024

Transition (non-forest → forest)	Area (ha)	Δ AGB (t d.m. ha ⁻¹)	Δ Biomass (t)	ΔC_G (t C)
Water -Trees	0.1	131.6	13.02	6.12
Flooded vegetation -Trees	0.49	111.6	55.13	25.91
Crops -Trees	4.22	111.6	471.29	221.51
Bare Ground -Trees	2.12	131.6	279.13	131.19
Rangeland -Trees	583.72	125.4	73,198.11	34,403.11

Δ AGB = AGB_{forest} – AGB_{non-forest}. ΔC_G denotes carbon gains from forest regeneration and was calculated as Δ Biomass \times 0.47. Values represent the total carbon gains accumulated over the period from 2017 to 2024.

Net biomass carbon change (ΔC_B) summary

Total carbon losses (ΔC_L) = 66,884.07 t C

Total carbon gains (ΔC_G) = 34,768.84 t C

$$\Delta C_B = \Delta C_G - \Delta C_L = 34,768.84 - 66,884.07 = -32,115.23 \text{ t C}$$

Overall, the study area experienced a net biomass carbon loss of 32,115.23 t C between 2017 and 2024, indicating that forest regeneration was insufficient to offset carbon emissions from forest conversion.

Table 6. Final Summary CO₂-Equivalent

Statistic	Transition	Area (ha)	AGB (t d.m. ha ⁻¹)	AGB (t d.m. ha ⁻¹)	Δ AGB (t d.m. ha ⁻¹)	ΔC (t C)	CO ₂ -eq (t CO ₂ -eq)
Minimum (best-case)	Trees -Water	4.98	98.7	0	-98.7	-231.1	-848.1
Median		5.53	131.6	0	-131.6	-342.13	-1,255.6
Maximum (worst-case)		6.08	164.5	0	-164.5	-469.8	-1,724.2
Minimum (best-case)	Trees -Flooded Vegetation	779.5	98.7	23	-75.7	-27,700	-101,659
Median/central		866.15	131.6	20	-111.6	-45,431	-166,233
Maximum (worst-case)		952.8	164.5	17	-147.5	-65,960	-242,053
Minimum (best-case)	Trees -Crops	1.589	98.7	23	-75.7	-56.55	-207.56
Median		1.766	131.6	20	-111.6	-92.63	-339.96
Maximum (worst-case)		1.943	164.5	17	-147.5	-134.67	-494.23
Minimum (best-case)	Trees -Rangeland	320.95	98.7	7.13	-91.57	-13,813.09	-50,677.0
Median		356.61	131.6	6.2	-125.4	-21,018.06	-77,126.3
Maximum (worst-case)		392.27	164.5	5.27	-159.23	-29,357.06	-107,726.4

Table 7. Net Biomass Carbon Change under Uncertainty

Scenario	ΔC_L (t C)	ΔC_G (t C)	ΔC_B (t C)
Minimum (best-case)	-41,800.74	34,768.84	-7,031.90
Median/central	-66,884.07	34,768.84	-32,115.23
Maximum (worst-case)	-95,921.53	34,768.84	-61,152.69

Across all uncertainty realizations, ΔC_L consistently exceeded ΔC_G , resulting in a median net biomass carbon loss of -32,115.23 t C.

Table 8. Monte Carlo Uncertainty Analysis

Transition	Median	2.50%	97.50%
Trees -Water	-341.37	-441.75	-252.16
Trees - Flooded vegetation	-45,284.15	-60,651.25	-31,658.65
Trees - Crops	-92.87	-124.11	-64.7

Trees - Rangeland	-20,977.80	-27,496.28	-15,246.86
Water - Trees	6.15	4.55	7.96
Flooded vegetation - Trees	25.56	17.84	34.37
Crops - Trees	221.19	154.21	295.21
Bare ground - Trees	131.02	96.1	169.55
Rangeland - Trees	34,363.53	24,876.90	44,881.73

The Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis shows that carbon losses from forest conversion, particularly transitions from trees to flooded vegetation and from trees to rangeland, consistently exceed gains from forest regeneration across all uncertainty realizations. Although rangeland regeneration represents a substantial carbon sink, it is insufficient to offset emissions from forest loss, confirming that the study area functions as a net carbon source.

Discussion

The following section interprets these results in relation to socio-economic, hydrological, and governance drivers.

Linking Observed Carbon Losses to Socio-Economic Drivers in a Developing-Country Context

The results indicate a substantial net loss of above-ground biomass carbon of 32,115.23 t C ($\approx 117,756$ t CO₂-eq) between 2017 and 2024, driven predominantly by forest conversion to flooded vegetation and rangeland (Tables 4–5). The dominance of transitions from trees to flooded vegetation (68.0%) and from trees to rangeland (31.4%) suggests that forest carbon losses in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest are not primarily associated with large-scale commercial agriculture, but rather with subsistence-oriented land use, smallholder expansion, and the utilization of hydrologically marginal landscapes. Such patterns are characteristic of developing-country forest systems, where forests function as critical livelihood safety nets yet remain weakly protected due to limited enforcement capacity and institutional constraints (Angelsen et al., 2018; Naing Tun et al., 2021). Myanmar's restricted access to alternative income sources, reliance on rain-fed agriculture, and continued dependence on forest resources for fuelwood and grazing intensify pressure on protected forest areas. These socio-economic conditions help explain why forest change is expressed predominantly as gradual degradation and canopy thinning, leading to conversion into low-biomass land-cover classes rather than abrupt, large-scale deforestation. Comparable transition-dominated degradation pathways have been widely reported across tropical developing regions, where poverty, population growth, and weak governance structures interact to sustain forest carbon emissions despite formal protection status (Achard et al., 2014; De Sy et al., 2019).

Hydrological Change as a Mediating Environmental Driver of Carbon Loss

The predominance of transitions from trees to flooded vegetation demonstrates that hydrological change is a key mediator of forest carbon loss in the study area. Expansion of flooded conditions driven by monsoon variability, upstream river regulation, and localized land degradation induces prolonged waterlogging, forest stress, and tree mortality, ultimately facilitating the replacement of forest cover by low-biomass flooded vegetation. This transition is associated with a pronounced reduction in above-ground biomass from 131.6 to 20 t d.m. ha⁻¹, generating substantial carbon losses even where overall forest-area change remains spatially limited.

In developing-country contexts such as Myanmar, limited investment in watershed management, drainage infrastructure, and climate adaptation strategies amplifies forest vulnerability to hydroclimatic extremes. Consistent with observations across Southeast Asia, the interaction between climate-induced flooding and anthropogenic disturbance accelerates forest degradation and carbon emissions without necessitating large-scale deforestation (Hansen et al., 2016; Leung et al., 2024). These findings highlight that, in

monsoon-dominated tropical systems, carbon losses within protected forests may be driven as much by environmentally mediated degradation as by direct land-use conversion, underscoring the importance of integrating hydrological management into forest carbon mitigation strategies.

Figure 3. Precipitation and Minimum and Maximum Temperature Derived from WorldClim (GIS-based analysis)

Forest Regeneration: Why Carbon Gains Remain Insufficient

Although measurable forest regeneration was observed, contributing 34,768.84 t C over the study period, transitions from rangeland to trees accounted for 99.0% of carbon increases (Table 5). This pattern reflects secondary forest recovery on previously degraded lands, a process commonly reported in developing countries where land abandonment occurs due to declining soil productivity, shifting livelihood strategies, or temporary reductions in land-use pressure. However, the limited spatial extent of regeneration (583.72 ha) and the relatively low biomass of young secondary forests substantially constrain their capacity to offset ongoing carbon losses from forest degradation.

The resulting imbalance between carbon losses and gains is consistent with evidence from tropical developing regions, where regeneration typically proceeds more slowly than degradation in both areal expansion and biomass accumulation (Hunka et al., 2024; Rozendaal et al., 2022). In the absence of active restoration measures, such as enrichment planting, assisted natural regeneration, or legal protection of recovering stands, secondary forests often remain trapped in low-carbon states for extended periods. Consequently, despite detectable regeneration, forest landscapes may continue to function as net carbon sources, reinforcing the need for targeted restoration and management interventions to enhance long-term carbon sequestration.

Governance Constraints and Policy Implications for REDD+ Implementation

The persistence of net carbon source behavior in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest highlights enduring governance constraints characteristic of developing countries, including insecure land tenure, limited enforcement capacity, and insufficient integration of local communities into forest management. Despite its formal designation as a protected area, the continued occurrence of forest-to-non-forest transitions indicates a pronounced gap between policy formulation and on-the-ground implementation. Assessments of REDD+ readiness in Myanmar similarly identify weak institutional coordination, fragmented governance structures, and constrained monitoring capacity as major barriers to effective carbon-based conservation (Angelsen et al., 2018).

From a policy perspective, the findings demonstrate that remote-sensing–based, IPCC Tier-1 carbon assessments offer a practical and scalable entry point for REDD+ measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV) in data-limited environments. However, monitoring alone cannot arrest carbon losses. The transition patterns observed in this study underscore the necessity of complementary governance and livelihood interventions, including community-based forest management, livelihood diversification beyond forest extraction, hydrological restoration in flood-prone areas, and legal protection of regenerating forest stands. Without addressing the underlying socio-economic and institutional drivers revealed by the transition analysis, protected forests in developing countries are likely to continue functioning as net carbon sources, despite formal conservation status and REDD+ engagement.

Conclusion

This study assessed land-use/land-cover change and forest carbon dynamics in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest, Myanmar (2017–2024), by integrating Sentinel-2 imagery with an IPCC Tier-1 transition-based stock-difference framework. Results indicate a net above-ground biomass carbon loss of 32,115.23 t C ($\approx 117,756$ t CO₂-eq), driven mainly by forest conversion to flooded vegetation and rangeland, while regeneration was insufficient to offset emissions.

By coupling pixel-level LULC transitions with IPCC default biomass coefficients and Monte Carlo uncertainty propagation, the study advances Tier-1 carbon accounting and confirms that the forest remained a net carbon source across all uncertainty scenarios. The findings highlight that degradation-driven and hydrologically mediated processes, rather than large-scale deforestation alone, dominate carbon losses in this protected forest. Overall, the study demonstrates that enhanced IPCC Tier-1 methods combined with high-resolution Earth observation can deliver robust, policy-relevant evidence to support REDD+ MRV and forest-carbon management in data-limited tropical regions.

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Appendix

Table 3. LULC Changes Transition Matrix for 2017 to 2024 (area in ha)

FID_Shwe_L	gridcode	Class_2017	Area_ha	FID_Shwe_1	gridcode_1	Class_2024	Area_ha_1	Change	Change_ha
0	1	Water	453.1580	0	1	Water	82.42680	Water - Water	48.23040
0	1	Water	453.1580	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Water - Trees	0.0989380
0	1	Water	453.1580	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Water - Flooded Vegetation	404.2460
0	1	Water	453.1580	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Water - Crops	0.1571410
0	1	Water	453.1580	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Water - Rangeland	0.1586290
1	2	Trees	18314.20	0	1	Water	82.42680	Trees - Water	5.531480
1	2	Trees	18314.20	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Trees - Trees	17081.10
1	2	Trees	18314.20	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Trees - Flooded Vegetation	866.1490
1	2	Trees	18314.20	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Trees - Crops	1.765970
1	2	Trees	18314.20	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Trees - Rangeland	356.6130
2	4	Flooded Vegetation	1286.410	0	1	Water	82.42680	Flooded Vegetation - Water	1.068540
2	4	Flooded Vegetation	1286.410	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Flooded Vegetation - Trees	0.4940060
2	4	Flooded Vegetation	1286.410	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Flooded Vegetation - Flooded Vegetation	1284.450
3	5	Crops	44.21180	0	1	Water	82.42680	Crops - Water	0.1152440
3	5	Crops	44.21180	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Crops - Trees	4.223070
3	5	Crops	44.21180	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Crops - Crops	30.8290
3	5	Crops	44.21180	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Crops - Rangeland	8.957980
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	0	1	Water	82.42680	Bare ground - Water	0.784660
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Bare ground - Trees	2.121060
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Bare ground - Flooded Vegetation	26.08180
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Bare ground - Crops	0.4346410
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Bare ground - Rangeland	2.732130
5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	0	1	Water	82.42680	Rangeland - Water	26.63890
5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Rangeland - Trees	583.7170

5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Rangeland - Flooded Vegetation	771.1320
5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Rangeland - Crops	7.041570
5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Rangeland - Rangeland	306.7110

